

DATA-COLLECTION IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM AND DIVERSIFICATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE BASIC CONCEPT OF TOURISM STATISTICS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides guidance on data - collection in the field of tourism and diversification and classification of the basic concept of tourism statistics

Nowadays, the spread of tourist connections in the world, the trans-nationalization of economic activity in the field of tourism, and the formation of a single tourist market have led to the need for international statistical dimensions of tourism. It is proposed to use consistent information based on a single methodology. Tourism statistics are becoming an integral part of the global statistical system. Therefore, the State Committee for Tourism Development has started to develop the methodology for the formation of regional tourism statistics according to UNWTO standards in order to ensure the implementation of the "Tourism Development Concept in 2019-2025" approved by the President's Decree No. 5611 dated January 5, 2019. This methodology is based on the collection of preliminary statistical data on regions, the development of statistical forms and questions for social questionnaires of tourist market subjects and consumers of tourist services. A common characteristic of statistical data is that they are generalizing quantities that do not refer to some isolated events, but always cover a set of them. A single event, unlike a set, is not divided into independent and similar structural elements. When a set is reduced to one or more occurrences, it retains its previous position rather than disappearing completely. For example, if one or more people among the population of the city die or move to another place, the population remains as a group.

According to the prominent economist E. Kane, the American reference work classification in administrative institutions defines statistics as follows: "Statistics is the science of collecting, classifying and quantifying facts as a basis for drawing conclusions." In this sense, it is the name of descriptive statistics. is also conducted with Descriptive statistics

are ways of collecting, classifying, summarizing and interpreting data. So, descriptive statistics refers to ways of collecting, classifying, summarizing and interpreting information. Its focus is on gathering and summarizing data. Descriptive statistics deals with the development and practical application of methods of effective data collection, organization, and obtaining generalized statistical information. The use of information technologies is an important issue in this work. Therefore, economists and statisticians should have a thorough knowledge of the rules of collecting, processing and storing information using information technologies.

400 years ago, the famous economist U. Petty, one of the founders of classical English politics, suggested changing the ratio of material and non-material production sectors to increase the second contribution. In the modern world economy, the role of the service sector, especially tourism, is rapidly increasing. According to the results of statistical research, the number of international tourist visits in the world increased by 41.4 times and the volume of international tourism increased by 512 times between 1950 and 2012. According to BTT, the number of visits by foreign tourists increased by 4.4% in 2015. This means that compared to 2014, more than 50 million tourists (overnight travelers) made international trips.

As a result of research, collecting touristic data and their statistical analysis, decision-making in the field of tourism makes the process of optimal development of the sector more effective, and this process includes different stages, we offer the following concept. **Fig. 1.**

Fig. 1. The concept of statistical data collection in tourism.

Based on this concept, it helps to make the industry more efficient and competitive by allowing to rely on accurate and based information for decision making in the tourism sector. The flow of information to tourism statistics is formed in two directions. The first stream determines the demand of consumers for tourist services. In this direction, socio-economic information on the size and structure of consumers of tourist services is studied: advantages, actual costs of consuming these services; ways and directions of spending free time; social and demographic composition of the population; propensity to pay of certain groups of consumers of tourist services. The second stream of information is related to the offer of tourism services resources. An example of this is natural, historical, social and cultural tourism resources. At the same time, accompanying services to tourist resources such as accommodation, excursions and transport; medical, financial, insurance, security services, etc.

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